

IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION PROCESSES ON THE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF COUNTRIES

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Abstract: this article provides insights into the impact of globalization processes on the economic development of countries and conducts research on this topic. Globalization is a change in the structure of the world economy, understood as a set of national economies connected to each other through the international division of labor, a system of economic and political relations. It is widely explained that it is one of the unique features of the processes.

Key words: Globalization, economy, transnational corporations, world economy, division of labor, international relations, capital, market, countries, national economy, production.

Introduction: Globalization is a worldwide process of economic, political, cultural and religious integration and convergence.

Globalization is one of the distinctive features of the processes of changing the structure of the world economy, which is understood as a set of national economies connected to each other through the international division of labor, the system of economic and political relations. Based on this, a single world network, market economy, geo-economy and its infrastructures are being formed, the influence of state sovereignty, which has been the main character of international relations for many centuries, is declining. The process of globalization is the result of the evolution of market systems formed by the state.

The main result of this is the global division of labor, global migration of capital, labor, production resources (also, as a rule, concentration), standardization of legislation, economic and technological processes, as well as the convergence and integration of cultures of different countries. Globalization has a systemic nature, that is, it is an objective process that covers all spheres of society's life. As a result of globalization, the world is connected and subordinated to all its subjects. There is an increase in the number of problems common to a group of states and an expansion in the number and types of unifying entities.

Globalization of the economy is one of the laws of world development. Compared to integration, the incomparable increase in the interdependence of the economies of different countries is associated with the formation of an economic space, in which the network structure, information and technology exchange, and the geography of the location of productive forces are determined taking into account the world. situation and economic ups and downs take on planetary proportions.

The ever-increasing globalization of the economy is expressed in the sharp increase in the volume and speed of capital movements, the outpacing of international trade growth in relation to the growth of the gross domestic product, and the emergence of world financial markets that work day and night in real time. The information systems created in recent decades have immeasurably increased the ability of financial capital to move quickly, which includes at least the ability to destroy stable economic systems. "Economic Dictionary" says: "Globalization of the economy is a complex and contradictory process. On the one hand, it facilitates economic cooperation between countries, creates conditions for countries to use the advanced achievements of mankind, ensures saving of resources, and stimulates world development.

On the other hand, globalization leads to negative consequences: the integration of the peripheral model of the economy, the loss of resources by countries that are not part of the "golden billion", the destruction of small

businesses, the spread of competition, weak countries of globalization, a decrease in the standard of living, etc. Bringing the effects of globalization to more countries in the world is one of the tasks facing the global community." The WTO stated that "since 1950, in recent decades, the volume of world trade has been growing much faster than the world's production." Thus, for the period 1950-2000. It increased 6 times". In 1999, "total exports made up 26.4% of world production, compared to 8% in 1950. "But globalization includes not only international trade, but also the transfer of production processes from one country to another, as well as the export of capital. As a rule, transnational corporations transfer production from high-wage (developed) countries to low-wage (developing) countries. This it leads to developed countries becoming post-industrial societies, and developing countries to industrialization. At the same time, international production is carried out both in enterprises owned by multinational corporations in foreign countries, and on the basis of contracts with independent local producers (known as maquiladoras in Mexico and other countries).

At the current stage of globalization, it is necessary to note the emergence of transnational corporations that operate independently of concrete state control in the economic sphere. Their control over a specific sector of the economy is not limited to a specific region, nation or culture. The International Monetary Fund, the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development, etc., which operate on a global scale, determine the policy on the direction of money flows, not on the financing of production. as a financial state, they have more opportunities than the budgets of several small and medium-sized countries. therefore, any country that wants to enter the world has to consider these conditions.

Elected employees are trained to work in transnational corporations, the International Monetary Fund and other international structures. As a result of the activities of these managers, various decisions were made at the global level, including decisions about how much to attract labor from poor countries to which of the developed countries.

In economic globalization, it is also forced to give up a part of the state's sovereignty for investments and technology made in a number of regions outside the West. and the consequences of this cannot but cause many negative aspects.

The driving forces and factors of the globalization of the world economy. The next logistic stage of the analysis of globalization should be to consider the factors that influence the globalization processes and directly shape them and the driving forces of globalization. At the end, it is possible to include the concentration and centralization of capital, which is gaining strength within the framework of the world economy, the transnationalization of economic life - the growth and development of large multinational companies and financial groups. Modern globalization processes are greatly influenced by such a powerful force as market competition, which promotes globalization not only in national markets, but also in global markets. The main means of competition - reducing costs, increasing the quality of goods and services, expanding their types - is the engine of globalization.

One of the driving forces of globalization is the development of scientific and technical progress, the development of technological innovations, which is more clearly manifested in the modification of transport and communication, information and telecommunication networks, the transfer of goods and services, financial instruments, ideas and information products to cross-border vehicles. creates unexpected opportunities for quick and low-cost deployment. The emergence of new information and communication technologies, high-speed computer technology, optical wave technology of signal transmission, satellite and mobile phone communication, cybernetics, network technologies, the development of compact electronic devices, the creation of the Internet global network, and the emergence of other technical achievements appeared with The discovery of completely new opportunities in the framework of information and communication technologies allows us to talk about real information innovations based on knowledge (knowledge-based) of the revolution, which stimulates the development

of globalization processes. According to current estimates and estimates, over the next 5-10 years, the total volume of available information in the world will double every half year: this is called Moore's Law (in honor of the person who first discovered this trend).

American researcher of international economic relations Dj. Garrett distinguishes three main mechanisms of globalization of the world economy, which include: 1) growing competition in world trade; 2) establishment of the multinational nature of production as a result of the desire of producers to increase their personal income due to the location of production facilities in other countries; 3) international integration of financial markets.

The processes of transnationalization in the world economy are embodied in the processes of creation of transnational corporations and their activities in the real and financial sectors. In the work of western economists, similar subjects of economic activity can be called transnational, international, multinational, supernational, global and other companies. Accordingly, the term "transnational corporation" means large financial, production, scientific-technical, trade-service associations, which organize their own operations and carry out the same in other foreign countries. They are distinguished from each other by a complex organizational structure that includes personal production, banking, investment, trade-advertisement activities, research and development activities, and personnel training.

The following are the modern distinguishing features of TNCs:

- Management of markets according to plan and implementation of global competition (some foreign experts use a new word for the modern term of global competition - "hypercompetition");
- Separation of world markets with such global corporations;

Monitoring the activities of their departments based on new information and communication technologies; flexibility of corporate structure; to unite its

departments, factories and joint enterprises into a single international management network;

- Economic and political influence on the country where TNC operates.

The first major development for any country will naturally be the domestic market (large countries have abnormal advantages in this), as long as, with the rise of transnationalization processes, the main criterion of political economic development is to enter the world market with modern products and stay there. z remains to have a place.

TNCs are economic entities that make the main part of the world's foreign direct investment (FDI). The latter dynamics are surprising: according to the 2002 International Investment Report, the average annual growth rate of TXI in the world was 20% in the first half of the 90s, and 40.1% in the second half. organized. Fixed capital as a share of direct foreign investments in the total volume of international investments increased from 2.0-2.4% in 1980 to 6-8% at the end of 1990.

Conclusion: The interaction of globalization and regionalization, territorial economic integration processes does not always have the same meaning. It is no secret that one of the characteristic features of the current state of the globalizing world economy is the formation of numerous regional economic groups. Simplistic notions of the interaction of regionalization (territorial economic integration) and globalization correspond to the position that one negates the other. For example, there are opinions that "international regionalization is a dialectical negation of globalization, as long as territorial unions include only a limited number of countries."

References:

1. Glebov G. I., Milaeva O. V. Fashional international communication. Educational Posobie. — Penza: Izd. penz. gos. universiteta, 2010. - 98 s.

2. 2. Korenyushkina Svetlana Ilyinichna, Solovyov Kirill Anatolievich (2015). Sovereignty in the era of globalization: theory and practice (Society. Environment. Development (Terra Humana) nashri).
3. Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Belarus, 2009. Cambridge Economic History of Europe, Cambridge, 1989, Vol. VIII, pp. 1, 90-91
4. „Shipping Container History: Boxes to Buildings“ (inglizcha). Discover Containers (25-mart 2015-yil).
5. Cambridge Economic History of Europe, Cambridge, 1989, Vol. VIII, p. 94
6. Globalizatsiya // Ekonomicheskiy slovar / A. I. Arxipov i dr.; otv. red. A. I. Arxipov. — 2-e izd., pererab. i dop. — M.: Prospekt, 2010. S. 136. — 6